

CONSERVATION TILLAGE, MOISTURE CONSERVATION AND COVER CROP MANAGEMENT ON YIELD AND YIELD ATTRIBUTES OF MAIZE (*Zea mays*) IN NORTHERN TRANSITION ZONE OF KARNATAKA, INDIA.

Kiran Kumar¹, H. B. Babalad² and Nandini K M³

1. Ph.D. Scholar department of Agronomy, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad, Karnataka, India
2. Professor of Agronomy and University Librarian, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dhrwad, Karnataka, India
3. Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Agronomy, University of Agricultural and Horticulture Sciences, Shivamogga, Karnataka, India

kirankamble.jk@gmail.com

(MS Received: 24.01.2023; MS Revised: 25.02.2023; MS Accepted: 26.03.2023)

MS 3009

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRONOMY.)

Abstract

Conservation tillage (CT) is an important tool in the development of sustainable agricultural systems around the world. It's proven very successful at sustaining agricultural production in semi-arid rain-fed areas. The study's goal was to determine the impact of tillage on maize vegetative development and yields, and it was driven by the following objectives. i) To evaluate the effect of tillage practice and cover crop management on vegetative growth of maize, and ii) evaluate the effect of tillage practice and cover crop management on maize yield. The experiment was conducted on a fixed site which, was initiated during 2013-14 in plot No. D 134 of D Block at MARS, UAS, Dharwad, Karnataka, with six tillage practices mainly conservation tillage with BBF and crop residues retained on the surface (CT₁); conservation tillage with BBF crop residue incorporation (CT₂); conservation tillage with flat bed with crop residues retained on the surface (CT₃); conservation tillage with flat bed with incorporation of crop residues (CT₄); conventional tillage with crop residues incorporation (CT₅) and conventional tillage with no crop residues (CT₆) were super imposed by two cover crop management mainly with and without cowpea cover crop were evaluated under rainfed farming situation at Main Agriculture Research Station (MARS), University of Agricultural Sciences Dharwad, during Kharif 2016 and 2017. The two years pooled data on yield and yield attributes showed that significantly higher cob weight per plant (159.48 g) grain weight per cob (119.66 g) grain yield (6470 kg ha⁻¹) and stover yield (7376 kg ha⁻¹) of maize was recorded in conservation tillage with BBF and incorporation of crop residues as compared to other tillage treatments. Among cover crop management without cover crop (6803 kg ha⁻¹) recorded significantly higher grain yield and stover yield (7969 kg ha⁻¹) as compared to with cover crop (6719 and 7754 kg ha⁻¹). The interaction of tillage practices and cover crop management differed significantly and conservation tillage with BBF and incorporation of crop residues without cover crop recorded significantly higher grain yield and stover yield (6993 and 8285 kg ha⁻¹) as compared to with cover crop.

Key Words: Conservation tillage, Cover crop, Broad bed and furrow (BBF), and Crop residues.

Introduction

Intensive tillage promotes excessive aggregate disintegration, resulting in soil erosion in areas with increased rainfall. Intensive tillage can also harm the environment by hastening soil carbon loss and increasing greenhouse gas emissions (Reicosky *et al.*, 2003). Tillage currently accounts for a larger percentage of production expenses than harvesting, because of recent rises in fuel prices (Edwards and Smith, 2005). Such techniques have sparked a search for tillage technologies that have minimal negative environmental implications while maintaining economic crop output. More recently, conservation tillage (no tillage with residue retention) was identified in recent literature reviews. Those concerned with sustainable agro-ecosystems see intensive tillage-based soil management as a developing problem (Gathala *et al.*, 2015). Soil fertility has been degraded as a result of the destructive nature of soil tillage and other activities, with long-term ramifications for agricultural productivity development and, eventually, food security (Morello *et al.*, 2018; Jat *et al.*, 2020). Most Asian countries face substantial issues in ensuring food security for a growing population and alleviating poverty while maintaining agricultural systems in the face of decreasing natural resources, negative impacts of climatic unpredictability, spiraling input costs, and volatile food prices (Suraj Bhan and Behera., 2014). In addition to these issues, soil erosion, soil organic matter loss, and salinization are the main indications of non-sustainability of agricultural system (Derpsch *et al.*, 2010; Derpsch *et al.*, 2011). Intensive tillage-induced soil organic matter loss, soil structural degradation, water and wind erosion, lower water penetration rates, surface sealing and crusting, soil compaction, insufficient organic material return, and monocropping are the main causes for this (Wolff and Stein, 1998). Improving soil quality is the principle strategy for sustaining agricultural production. Increasing the biomass production, decreasing losses of soil, water and nutrients from ecosystem, fostering soil bio-diversity and strengthening nutrient

cycling mechanisms would improve soil quality and its productivity (Monther *et al.*, 2020). There is also evidence that, globally, soils have the capacity to accommodate the addition of substantial amount of carbon from atmosphere by photosynthesis and sequester it for long enough time to significantly reduce the accumulation rate of atmospheric carbon dioxide (Lefevre Clara, *et al.*, 2017).

Conservation agriculture (CA), a concept that arose in response to global concerns about agriculture's sustainability. Farmers worldwide are increasingly adopting conservation agriculture. In the 2015-16 season, conservation agriculture was practiced on about 180 mega hectares of cropland globally, about 12.5% of the total global cropland 69% more than in the 2008-2009 season (Mary Donovan, 2020). CA is a resource-conserving agricultural production system that strives to achieve high yields and production intensification while preserving the natural resource base by adhering to three interconnected principles, as well as other sound plant nutrition and pest management methods (Abrol and Sangar., 2006). An understanding of the fundamental components of conservation agriculture is imperative in order to appreciate the necessity for weed control strategies in these practices as well as the difficulties associated with their development. To that aim, our purpose, in part, is to study the effect of conservation tillage moisture conservation and cover crop management on growth and yield of maize.

Material and Methods

The experiment was conducted at Main Agricultural Research Station (MARS), University of Agricultural Sciences (UAS), Dharwad, Karnataka on a fixed site during 2016 and 2017 in plot No. D 103 of D Block, which is located at 15° 26'N latitude and 75° 7' E longitude and at an altitude of 678 m above the mean sea level. According to NARP Agro-climatic classification MARS, comes under the Northern Transition Zone (Zone 8) of Karnataka, which lies in between the

Western high rainfall Hilly Zone (Zone 9) and low rainfall Northern Dry Zone (Zone 3) of Karnataka. The mean annual rainfall for the past 65 years at MARS, Dharwad is 711.44 mm, which is well distributed from June to October with two peaks, received one in the month of July (153.48 mm) and another during October (124.52 mm). In all the conservation tillage treatments, crop residues produced in the system were retained on the surface till April end. The treatments were imposed during first week of May. In conservation tillage with flatbed and BBF plots, rotovator was used for surface shredding and surface incorporation of crop residues and rotoslasher was used for shredding and crop residues were retained as mulch on the surface and no tillage operations were carried out later. In conventional tillage with crop residues treatment the land was ploughed with mould board plough and incorporated the crop residues and in conventional tillage without crop residues the residues were removed and land was ploughed with mould board plough. In both the treatments the clods were crushed by cultivating with cultivator and harrow and soil was brought to fine tilth. Well decomposed FYM for maize at the rate of 5 t ha⁻¹ was incorporated into the soil fifteen days before sowing. The recommended chemical fertilizers for maize (100:50:25 kg N, P₂O₅ and K₂O ha⁻¹). For maize, 50 per cent of nitrogen and full dose of phosphorus and potassium were applied at the time of sowing as basal and remaining 50 per cent of nitrogen was applied at 60 days after sowing (DAS). The experiment plot was laid out as per the plan of layout. While sowing one row was skipped for every 6 rows of 30 cm apart and in a skipped row furrow was formed to prepare a broad bed and furrows with a bed width of 120 cm and 30 cm furrow immediately after sowing of the crops. The opened furrows help for conservation of water and also to drain excess water. Cobs along with rind and husk from the randomly selected five plants at the time of harvesting from the net plot were weighed separately. The average weight was recorded in g plant⁻¹. The grains from the sun dried cobs of five randomly selected plants were separated and weighed. The average weight was recorded as grain weight per plant in grams. Hundred seeds were randomly counted from the sample drawn from the net plot yield for each treatment. The weight was recorded and expressed in grams. After physiological maturity of the crop the cobs were harvested treatment wise. Harvested cobs were air dried, shelled and grains were cleaned and weighed individually. Grain yield per hectare was computed from the net plot and was expressed in kg ha⁻¹. Stover yield was recorded after complete sun drying of stalks from the net plot from each treatment and expressed in kg ha⁻¹. Harvest index is the ratio of economic yield to the biological yield (Donald, 1962) and expressed in per cent.

Result and discussion

Growth of a plant is an outcome of series of internal biological events involving biochemical, physiological and morphological changes which take place during its development in accordance with the resources *viz.*, light, moisture, temperature and nutrients, resulting in synthesis, accumulation and translocation of photosynthates. Yield is related to both total assimilation achieved during season and the way material acquired is portioned between harvestable storage structure and the rest of the parts and these factors are controlled by environment under which crop is grown. Conservation agriculture (CA) is an alternate to conventional agriculture with combination of resource conservation practices. These agricultural practices are lower disturbances to soil through reduced tillage or no-tillage and direct sowing, covering the soil through crop residues or mulching, cover crops and intercrops to mitigate soil erosion as well as improve the soil fertility and soil functions, crop rotation to control weeds, insect-pests and diseases (Derpsch, 2001). Main aim of CA is to boost agricultural production by increasing the efficiency of farm resources and facilitating to reduce land degradation through integrated management of available land, water and natural resources combined with external

inputs. Conventional tillage is replaced by mixing of the soil by the activity of soil flora including plant roots and soil fauna will take over the tillage function and improve the soil physical condition and soil nutrients balancing. Soil fertility is handled and balanced by soil cover management, crop rotations and weed management (SoCo, 2009). According to FAO, conservation agriculture (CA) is an approach to managing agro-ecosystems for improved and sustained productivity, increased profits and food security while preserving and enhancing the resource base and the environment.

In the present investigation, two years pooled data on grain yield of maize differed significantly. Significantly higher grain yield was recorded in conservation tillage with BBF and incorporation of crop residues as (6939 kg ha⁻¹) as compared to conventional tillage with and without crop residue (6836 and 6326 kg ha⁻¹ respectively) (Table 2). Increase in yield of conservation tillage plots over conventional is mainly because of favorable soil moisture condition throughout crop growing period resulted in more available soil nutrients due to mineralization by microbial activity may influenced the good crop growth and yield increment. Increase in yield in conservation tillage was also due to lower weed population and lower pest and disease incidence which might have resulted in higher rate of photosynthesis. The higher yield grain yield mainly attributed to higher cob weight per plant (159.48 g) higher grain weight per cob (115.90 g) and higher 100 grain weight (26.65) (Table 2). The higher yield parameters were also due to higher availability and absorption nutrients which might have influenced cell elongation, cell division, increased chlorophyll content and root development in turn resulting in higher yield (Kashif *et al.*, 2006; Sarma and Gautam, 2010 and Singh *et al.*, 2011). Because maize is an exhaustive crop requires more nutrients and more sensitive to both moisture stress and excess moisture conditions which are maintained in at normal conditions in conservation tillage treatment (Thierfelder *et al.*, 2005) observed increase productivity of maize based cropping systems in no tillage bed planting to the tune of 18 to 35 % increment in the yield of sequential crops. In permanent beds better aeration and high infiltration with good soil moisture availability may favor the crop growth. The conservation tillage practices improved soil moisture at different depths from sowing to harvest of the crops and also enhanced the soil fertility and nutrient availability to the crops. Similar results were reported by Rakesh *et al.* (2016). Grain yield is the product of harvest index and total dry matter production. The increase in harvest index with conservation tillage was noticed as compared to conventional tillage these results are in conformity with findings of many workers (Chopra and Angiras, 2008 and Sarma and Gautham, 2010). Grain yield is a cumulative expression of grain yield per plant, which in turn depends on yield attributes of maize *viz.*, 100 grain weight, cob weight per plant and grains weight per cob (Patil, 1998). The increase in grain yield per plant was mainly due to increased supply of nitrogen, photosynthates and water to the growing ear, leading to lower competition for light, aeration and nutrients. Further 100 grain weight was noticed in conservation tillage. Similarly, other yield components were higher with conservation tillage which resulted in higher grain yield in conservation tillage. Bigger cob size in conservation tillage with higher soil moisture content in the soil profile throughout the crop growth might have increased the number of grains with a provision for proper development of grains and led to higher 100 grain weight. These results are in conformity with the findings of Sarma and Gautam (2010) and Bahar (2013). The higher yield and yield components in conservation tillage were due to increased growth parameters. Conservation tillage recorded significantly higher total dry matter production at all the stages as compared to conventional tillage practices. This was mainly due to better harvesting of solar radiation and higher chlorophyll content which helped the plant to accumulate more photosynthates in leaves and stem (Choudhary *et al.*, 2012).

Table 1 Cob weight, grain weight and 100 grain weight of maize as influenced by different conservation tillage and cover crop management practices (2016-17, 2017-18 and pooled)

Treatments Tillage practices	Cob weight plant ⁻¹			Grain weight cob ⁻¹			100 grain weight (g)		
	2016-17	2017-18	Pooled	2016-17	2017-18	Pooled	2016-17	2017-18	Pooled
CT ₁	165.19a	150.44a	157.82a	120.42a	113.00ab	116.71ab	27.43a	25.54ab	26.48a
CT ₂	166.95a	152.01a	159.48a	123.42a	115.90a	119.66a	26.69bc	25.64ab	26.16a
CT ₃	161.77ab	150.83a	156.30ab	117.59a	109.47b	113.53b	26.89ab	26.41a	26.65a
CT ₄	161.23ab	147.54ab	154.38ab	118.84a	113.67ab	116.26ab	26.86ab	25.92ab	26.39a
CT ₅	155.70b	146.44ab	151.07b	114.95a	110.32b	112.63b	26.35c	24.15bc	25.25b
CT ₆	147.17c	141.58b	144.37c	104.14b	99.67c	101.90c	25.19d	23.16c	24.17c
S.Em ±	2.54	1.56	1.96	2.80	1.51	1.75	0.17	0.54	0.27
CC management									
CC ₁	157.30b	146.69b	151.99b	115.18b	109.07b	112.13b	26.07b	24.59b	25.33b
CC ₂	162.03a	149.60a	155.81a	117.93a	111.61a	114.77a	27.06a	25.68a	26.37a
S.Em ±	1.23	0.71	0.90	0.78	0.53	0.27	0.21	0.49	0.21
Interactions (CT X CC)									
CT ₁ CC ₁	163.64a-c	149.33ab	156.48b-d	118.35ab	111.77a-c	115.06bc	27.02a	24.88bc	25.95a-c
CT ₁ CC ₂	166.75ab	151.55ab	159.15ab	122.48ab	114.24ab	118.36ab	27.84a	26.19ab	27.02a
CT ₂ CC ₁	164.72a-c	150.12ab	157.42bc	120.47ab	112.65ab	116.56bc	26.20ab	25.17a-c	25.69a-c
CT ₂ CC ₂	169.19a	153.91a	161.55a	126.36a	119.16a	122.76a	27.18a	26.11ab	26.64a
CT ₃ CC ₁	159.26a-d	149.73ab	154.49c-d	115.41a-c	107.92bc	111.66c	26.56ab	25.95ab	26.25ab
CT ₃ CC ₂	164.27a-c	151.93ab	158.10a-c	119.77ab	111.02a-c	115.39bc	27.22a	26.86a	27.04a
CT ₄ CC ₁	159.23a-d	146.40ab	152.82d-e	116.91a-c	111.48a-c	114.19bc	26.37ab	25.67ab	26.02a-c
CT ₄ CC ₂	163.22a-c	148.69ab	155.95b-e	120.78bc	115.87ab	118.32ab	27.36a	26.18ab	26.77a
CT ₅ CC ₁	154.07cd	145.54ab	149.80fg	113.25bc	108.97a-c	111.11c	25.87ab	23.50cd	24.69c
CT ₅ CC ₂	157.34b-d	147.34ab	152.34ef	116.65a-c	111.67a-c	114.16bc	26.82a	24.80bc	25.81a-c
CT ₆ CC ₁	142.91e	139.00b	140.95h	106.71cd	101.63cd	104.17d	24.40b	22.38bc	23.39d
CT ₆ CC ₂	151.43de	144.16b	147.79g	101.58d	97.70d	99.64d	25.97ab	23.94d	24.95bc
S.Em ±	3.12	4.21	3.40	3.37	3.05	1.69	0.66	0.52	0.40

CT₁: Conservation tillage with BBF and crop residues retained on the surfaceCT₂: Conservation tillage with BBF and incorporation of crop residuesCT₃: Conservation tillage with flat bed with crop residues retained on the surfaceCT₄: Conservation tillage with flat bed with incorporation of crop residuesCT₅: Conventional tillage with crop residues incorporationCT₆: Conventional tillage (flat bed and no crop residues)CC₁: With cover cropCC₂: Without cover crop

Table 2 Grain yield, stover yield and harvest index of maize as influenced by different conservation tillage and cover crop management practices (2016-17, 2017-18 and pooled)

Treatments	Grain yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			Stover yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			Harvest index (%)		
	2016-17	2017-18	Pooled	2016-17	2017-18	Pooled	2016-17	2017-18	Pooled
Tillage practices									
CT ₁	7211b	6298c	6754c	8743a	7214a	7978a	42.65a	43.30a	42.98a
CT ₂	7427a	6470a	6939a	8916a	7223a	8069a	42.45a	43.63a	43.04a
CT ₃	7408a	6336bc	6881ab	8892a	7376a	8134a	41.80a	42.20a	42.00a
CT ₄	7287ab	6368a-c	6828bc	8739a	7261a	7999a	42.33a	42.73a	42.53a
CT ₅	7244b	6429ab	6836bc	8684a	7159a	7921a	38.78b	38.66b	38.72b
CT ₆	6738c	5915d	6326d	7732b	6403b	7067b	41.75a	41.52a	41.63a
S.Em ±	71.21	65.34	54.76	192.58	157.02	132.83	0.60	0.62	0.45
CC management									
CC ₁	7183b	6255b	6719b	8623b	7085b	7754b	42.00b	41.85b	41.92b
CC ₂	7255a	6351a	6803a	8812a	7526a	7969a	41.26a	42.16a	41.71a
S.Em ±	48.13	29.74	38.91	91.62	85.60	75.97	0.67	0.13	0.37
Interactions (CT X CC)									
CT ₁ CC ₁	7160.02c	6256b	6708c	8611a-c	7199ab	7905b	42.90a	43.21ab	43.06a
CT ₁ CC ₂	7261a-c	6340ab	6801bc	8876a-c	7228ab	8052ab	42.41ab	43.40ab	42.90ab
CT ₂ CC ₁	7420ab	6416a	6884b	8736ab	7142ab	7939b	42.73ab	43.70a	43.22a
CT ₂ CC ₂	7433ab	6523b	6993a	9096a-c	7303ab	8199ab	42.16ab	43.56a	42.86ab
CT ₃ CC ₁	7353a-c	6265ab	6842ab	8650a-c	7314ab	7982ab	42.27ab	42.16bc	42.22a-d
CT ₃ CC ₂	7462a	6406ab	6920ab	9133a	7437a	8285a	41.32ab	42.23bc	41.78cd
CT ₄ CC ₁	7271a-c	6313a	6792bc	8546bc	7197ab	7871b	42.65ab	42.69ab	42.67a-c
CT ₄ CC ₂	7304a-c	6424b	6864b	8932a-c	7323ab	8128ab	42.01ab	42.78ab	42.39a-c
CT ₅ CC ₁	7230bc	6424ab	6827bc	8493c	7323ab	7908b	39.08c	37.81e	38.45e
CT ₅ CC ₂	7258a-c	6434ab	6844b	8874a-c	6994b	7934b	38.49c	39.50d	38.99e
CT ₆ CC ₁	6666d	5854ab	6260d	7503d	6334c	6918c	42.34ab	41.52c	41.93b-d
CT ₆ CC ₂	6810d	5976d	6393e	7960d	6472c	7216c	41.15b	41.51c	41.33d
S.Em ±	65.30	56.00d	37.92	166.40	102.54	95.31	0.51	0.35	0.30

CT₁: Conservation tillage with BBF and crop residues retained on the surfaceCT₂: Conservation tillage with BBF and incorporation of crop residuesCT₃: Conservation tillage with flat bed with crop residues retained on the surfaceCT₄: Conservation tillage with flat bed with incorporation of crop residuesCT₅: Conventional tillage with crop residues incorporationCT₆: Conventional tillage (flat bed and no crop residues)CC₁: With cover cropCC₂: Without cover crop

References

1. **Abrol and Sangar, 2006.** Long-term tillage and rotation effects on properties of a central Ohio soil. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 58:517-522.
2. **Bahar, FA., 2013**, Relative performance of resource conservation technologies in maize based cropping system under temperate Kashmir. *Trends Biosci.*, 6 (1): 43-45.
3. **Chopra, P. and Angiras, NN., 2008**, Effect of tillage and weed management on productivity and nutrient uptake of maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Indian J. Agron.*, 53(1): 66-69.
4. **Choudhary, V. K., Suresh Kumar, P. and Bhagawati, R., 2012**, Production potential, soil moisture and temperature as influenced by maize-legume intercropping. *Int. J. Sci., Nature*, 3(1): 41-46.
5. **Derpsch, R., 2001**, Conservation Agriculture, a Worldwide Challenge, Proceedings of the First World Congress on Conservation Agriculture, Madrid, 1: 161-170. <http://www.rolf-derpsch.com>.
6. **Derpsch, R., Friedrich, T., Kassam, A. & Li, H.W. (2010)**. Current status of adoption of no-till farming in the world and some of its main benefits. *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering*, 3, 1-25.
7. **Derpsch, R., Friedrich, T., Landers, J. N., Rainbow, R., Reicosky, D. C., Sa', J. C. M., Sturny, W. G., Wall, P., Ward, R. C. & Weiss, K., (2011)**. About the necessity of adequately defining no-tillage – a discussion paper. In *Proc. 5th World Congr. Conserv. Agric.*, 26-29 September 2011, Brisbane, Australia.
8. **Donald, CM., 1962**, In search of yield. *J. Aus. Inst. Agric. Sci.*, 28: 171-178.
9. **Edwards, W. and D. Smith. 2005** Iowa custom farm rate survey. Ames: Iowa State University.
10. **Gathala, M. K., Timsina, J., Islam, M. S., Rahman, M. M., Hossain, M. I., Harun-Ar- Rashid, M.d., Ghosh, A. K., Krupnik, T. J., Tiwari, T. P., & McDonald, A. (2015)**. Conservation agriculture based tillage and crop establishment options can maintain farmers' yields and increase profits in South Asia's rice-maize systems: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Field Crops Research*, 172, 85–98.
11. **Jat, M. L., Chakraborty, D., Ladha, J. K., Rana, D. S., Gathala, M. K., McDonald, A., & Gerard, B. (2020)**. Conservation agriculture for sustainable intensification in South Asia. *Nature Sustainability*, 3(4), 336–343. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-0500-2>.
12. **Kashif, K., Iqbal, M., Arif, M. S. and Nawaz, A., 2006**, Effect of tillage and mulch on soil physical properties and growth of maize. *Int. J. Agric. Biol.*, 8(5): 593–596.
13. **Lefèvre Clara, Reik F, Alcantara Viridiana, Wiese Liesl. 2017**. Soil organic carbon the hidden potential. Soil Organic Carbon: the hidden potential. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Rome, Italy
14. **Mary Donovan, 2020** CIMMYT <https://www.cimmyt.org/news/what-is-conservation>
15. **Monther M. Tahat, Kholoud M. Alananbeh, Yahia A. Othman and Daniel I. Leskovar . 2020**. Soil Health and Sustainable Agriculture. *Sustainability*, 12, 4859
16. **Morello, T. F., Marie-Gabrielle, P., Gardner, T., Parry, L., Barlow, J., Ferreira, J., & Tancredi, N. S. (2018)**. Fertilizer Adoption by Smallholders in the Brazilian Amazon: Farm-level Evidence. *Ecological Economics*, 144, 278–291
17. **Patil, P. L., 1998**, Response of *rabi* sorghum to tillage, moisture conservation practices, organics and nitrogen in vertisols of semi – arid tropics. *Ph. D. Thesis*, Univ. Agric. Sci., Dharwad, Karnataka (India).
18. **Rakesh, C., Parvinder, S., Sidhu, H. S., Nandal, D. P., Jat, H. S., Yadvinder, S. and Jat, M. L., 2016**, Evaluation of tillage and crop establishment methods integrated with relay seeding of wheat and mungbean for sustainable intensification of cotton-wheat system in South Asia. *Field Crop Res.*, 199: 31-41.
19. **Reicosky, D. C. and Allmaras R. R 2003**. Advances in tillage research in North American cropping systems. *J. Crop Prod.* 8: 75-125,
20. **Sarma, CK. and Gautam, RC., 2010**, Weed growth, yield and nutrient uptake in maize (*Zea mays*) as influenced by tillage, seed rate and weed control method. *Indian J. Agron.*, 55(4): 299-303.
21. **Singh, D., Vyas, AK., Gupta, GK. Ramteke, R. and Khan, IR., 2011**, Tractor-drawn broad bed furrow seed drill machine to overcome moisture stress for soybean (*Glycine max*) in Vertisols. *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 81(10): 941–944.
22. **SoCo (Sustainable agriculture and soil conservation), 2009**, Soil-friendly farming systems and practices: Conservation agriculture. <http://eusoiils.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/SOCO/FactSheets/ENFactSheet-05.pdf>.
23. **Suraj Bhan and U. K. Behera, 2014**. Conservation agriculture in India – Problems, prospects and policy issues. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, 2(4): 1-12
24. **Thierfelder, C., Amezquita, E., Stahr, K., 2005**. Effects of intensifying organic manuring and tillage practices on penetration resistance and infiltration rate. *Soil Till. Res.*, 82, 211–226.
25. **Wolff, P., & Stein, T. M. (1998)**. Water efficiency and conservation in agriculture-opportunities and limitations. *Agriculture and Rural Development*, 5(2), 17-20.